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COVER ART – Illustration by Jason Poole of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Drexel University. A juvenile or diminutive species of hadrosaurid dinosaur is scavenged by multiple sharks in a shallow, near-shore marine setting.

NEW SPECIMENS OF LATE CRETACEOUS / EARLY PALEOCENE BIRD ELEMENTS FROM NEW JERSEY

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Abstract – This paper reports on four newly discovered fossil bird elements from the Hornerstown Formation of New Jersey. These specimens are Latest Cretaceous or Earliest Paleogene in age. The new specimens include two carpometacarpi a pedal phalange and a tibiotarsus. A complete list of all the known specimens of Late Cretaceous / Early Paleocene birds from New Jersey is also provided.

INTRODUCTION

Fossils of late Cretaceous / Early Paleocene birds are scarce and difficult to interpret. They are often fragmentary, disarticulated specimens: the result of rough fossilization processes on light-weight fragile bones. The principal areas of North America that have yielded fossil birds from this period are the inland deposits of the Hell Creek and Lance Formations in Wyoming (Brodkorb, 1963, Parris and Hope, 2002; Hope 2002, Hope and Parris 2006) and the marine deposits of New Jersey.

The first fragments of fossil birds found in North America came from the marl beds of New Jersey in 1834 and were first described by Marsh (1870, 1872) over a century ago. These specimens came from the Navesink Formation, which is clearly Maastrichtian or from the overlying Hornerstown Formation, which has been shown to contain a mix of typically Late Cretaceous and Early Paleocene material. The early specimens, recovered during most of the marl mining operations of the 19th century were described based on comparisons with extant birds. They were grouped into nine species in four genera (Marsh, 1870, 1872, 1873, 1877; Shufeldt, 1915). Over the years reviewers have placed these specimens with

birds in a diverse array of groups, including Galliformes, Anseriformes, Gruiformes, Charadriiformes and Phalacrocoracidae (Marsh 1870, 1872; Shuldfelt 1915, Lambrecht 1933; Rapp 1942; Wetmore 1956; Brodkorb 1963; Cracraft 1972, 1973).

More recent reviewers have focused instead on the similarities amongst these birds. Olson (1985), and Olson and Parris (1987) considered them early Charadriiformes and assembled them into a new form family, Graculavidae, while making synonyms of some specimens, referring new specimens to existing species and describing one new species. Olson (1999) also reclassified one species, bringing the number of species to 7 grouped into 6 genera. Parris and Hope (2002) defined two new species and further refined the list of New Jersey specimens so that it contained 9 species in 8 genera.

The following institutional abbreviations are used herein: ANSP – Academy of Natural Sciences Philadelphia, NJSM – New Jersey State Museum, YPM – Yale University Peabody Museum.

LOCALITIES

Confirmed Late Cretaceous / Early Paleocene birds have been found in only three different geographic locations in New Jersey with two other sites in New Jersey possibly yielding bird specimens (Figure 1). Most of the specimens described by Marsh (1870, 1872), except for *Laornis*, came from Upper Freehold Township, Monmouth County, in the area including the settlements of Hornerstown, Cream Ridge and Arneytown (see Figure 1, site H). These specimens could have come from the Navesink Formation or the overlying basal Hornerstown Formation, both of which are Maastrichtian in age (Olson and Parris 1987).

The second locality is near Birmingham, Burlington County. This is the site where *Laornis* was found in “greensand of the upper, Cretaceous marl bed... in the pits of Pembertown Marl Company” (Marsh 1870, 1872). Baird (1967) concluded that this specimen was latest Cretaceous (Olson and Parris 1987).

The third locality and by far the most abundant in its production of bird specimens is the Inversand Company marl pit, located in Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County, NJ. The stratigraphy of the site has been reviewed by Olson and Parris (1987) and Gallagher and Parris (1996). Many of the Inversand specimens come from the main fossiliferous layer (MFL) within the basal portion of the Hornerstown formation (Figure 2) which overlays the Maastrichtian Navesink formation.

The MFL is a narrow, 30 cm thick, well defined, densely fossiliferous layer. It contains Maastrichtian macrofossils such as ammonites and mosasaurs in a matrix that also includes Paleocene fossils. Because of this mix, the age of bird specimens from this layer has been frequently debated (Wetmore 1930; Richards and Gallagher, 1974).

There is a 3m layer of Hornerstown sediment overlying the MFL which is entirely Paleocene and which has yielded few vertebrate fossils (Parris 1986).

According to Gallagher (1996), this represents a massive disturbance in the marine food chain in the Early Paleocene. For this reason early specimens collected from the “Hornerstown” without precise Stratigraphic information are assumed to be from the MFL, but their age remains uncertain.

Figure 1: Localities in Southern New Jersey that have yield Late Cretaceous / Early Paleocene Birds; S = Sewell, B = Birmingham, H = Hornerstown, E = Ellisdale, BB = Big Brook (Adapted with permission from Olson and Parris 1987)

There are no biostratigraphic dates on the order of 100,000 years encompassing the MFL. Elevated levels of iridium have been found, but with no clear well defined peaks. This has been interpreted to mean that the MFL is a time averaged assemblage that accumulated sometime during the missing 100,000 years, made up of remains of a protracted faunal die-off at the end of the Cretaceous. More battered specimens, such as ammonites, are probably from early in the interval (Cretaceous) and other articulated and unworn specimens, including most of the birds, are more probably from a phase of deposition in the earliest Paleocene (Hope 2002).

The Inversand site also contains spoil piles, or sediments left over after the extraction process of glauconite “green sand”. Several specimens have been discovered in these piles by surface collecting and screening. No precise stratigraphic information is available for specimens from the spoil piles. Although presumably from the Hornerstown Formation, they could be either or Late Cretaceous or Early Paleocene.

In addition to these three locations, the New Jersey State Museum contains Aves specimens from two other locations in New Jersey of Cretaceous age; Ellisdale and Big Brook, both in Monmouth County. These specimens are tentatively listed as *Aves* but have not been formally described in any paper. The specimens are listed in Table 1.

REVIEW OF NJ SPECIMENS

Table 1 provides a complete list of all the late Cretaceous – Early Paleocene bird fossils found in New Jersey. There are 9 species in 8 genera encompassing 27 total specimens. The table provides the available historical data for each genera, listing the holotype as well as details on synonyms and reclassifications made by various reviewers over the years, as well as details on each specimen. The table includes 3 specimens from Inversand, 4 specimens

from Ellisdale, and 1 from the Big Brook sites, which have tentatively been identified as *Aves*, but have not been formally described.

Figure 2: Stratigraphic diagram of the Inversand marl pit in Sewell, NJ. (Courtesy of Wayne Callahan, Bill Gallagher and Jason Schein)

NEW SPECIMENS

Aves, incertae sedis

Referred Material – Distal right end of carpometacarpus, NJSM 20692, Plate 1 (B-D).

Locality and Horizon – Inversand Company marl pit, Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County,

New Jersey; from processed spoil piles, precise stratum unknown; collected by Gene Hess and Sally Shelton.

Measurements – The fragment is 9.5 mm in length and 4.1 mm at its widest point. The distal head is 4mm wide, and the shaft just below the head is 1.95 mm.

Plate 1 (A and B) shows a comparison of NJSM 20692 with the carpometacarpus of *Zenaidura macroura* (Mourning Dove). No specific conclusions are drawn from this comparison other than these two specimens may represent birds of similar size.

Referred Material – Pedal phalanx, NJSM 20693, Plate 1 (E-H).

Locality and Horizon- Inversand Company marl pit, Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County, New Jersey; from processed spoil piles, precise stratum unknown; collected by Gene Hess and Sally Shelton.

Measurements – The specimen is 11 mm in length. The shaft is 1.5 mm wide at the mid-point. The proximal head is 2.2 mm x 2.4 mm and the distal head is 3.1 mm x 2.5 mm.

Referred Material –*cf.* carpometacarpus - fragment, NJSM 21857, Plate 1 (I-L).

Locality and Horizon – Inversand Company marl pit, Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County, New Jersey; from processed spoil piles, precise stratum unknown; collected 28 April 2007 by Kyle Shankle. The age of this specimen could be either

Late Cretaceous or Early Paleocene or with the former age being more probable because most Cretaceous elements appear to be lag remanee components. Furthermore this specimen is delicate and hollow, making it unlikely to have withstood any protracted period of winnowing and wear (Gallagher 2007, personal correspondence).

Measurements – The specimen is 19 mm in length and is 4.3 mm wide at the mid-point. The end in Plate 1-K is 4.4 mm x 3.5 mm. The end in Plate 1-L is 5.3 mm x 4 mm.

Referred Material - *cf.* tibiotarsus - shaft fragment, NJSM 21871, Plate 1 (M-P).

Locality and Horizon – Inversand Company marl pit, Sewell, Mantua Township, Gloucester County, New Jersey; from stratum above the Most Fossiliferous Layer (MFL), exact distance to MFL uncertain but estimated at less than 300 mm (found as "float"), Hornerstown Fm.; collected by Jason Schein on 9 April 2008.

Measurements – The shaft fragment is 67.5 mm in length, and has an average diameter of 6 mm, which progressively widens gently toward one end, reaching its widest point at that terminus (8.5 mm).

Plate 1: *Zenaidura macroura* NJSM-B-7, (A – distal view for comparison to NJSM 20692 Palmer View – B), NJSM 20692 - Distal right end of carpometacarpus (B - palmar view, C – extensor view, D –distal view), NJSM 20693 - Pedal phalanx (E - plantar view, F - dorsal view, G –proximal view, H - distal view), NJSM 21857 *cf.* carpometacarpus, fragment (I – *cf.* Palmar view, J – *cf.* Extensor view, K –transverse cross section of the shaft (*cf.* distal view), L –*cf.* proximal view, NJSM 21871 (M, N – views of opposite sides of shaft, O –transverse cross section *cf.* distal view, P –cross section *cf.* proximal view)

Table 1: Late Cretaceous / Early Paleocene Bird Specimens from New Jersey

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
Charadriiformes (shore birds)	"Form Family Graculavidae"	<i>Graculavus velox</i> Marsh 1872 ¹	YPM 855 (Holotype) Marsh 1872:363 Shufeldt 1915:17 Olson & Parris 1987:4	Basal Hornerstown or Navesink	Hornerstown, Upper Freehold Township	Proximal end of left humerus with a short shaft
			NJSM 11854² Olson & Parris 1987:6 Hope 2004:359	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Worn and abraded major right metacarpal with fragments of the distal symphysis of the carpometacarpus.
		<i>Telmatornis priscus</i> ³ Marsh 1870 ⁴	YPM 840 (Holotype) Marsh 1870:210 Shufeldt 1915:26 Cracraft 1972:39 Olson & Parris 1987:6 Hope 2004:360	Navesink	Cream Ridge Marl Company, Hornerstown	Distal end of left humerus
			YPM 845 Holotype of <i>T. affinis</i> , Marsh 1870:211 Shufeldt 1915:27 Cracraft 1972:39 Olson & Parris 1987:6	Navesink	Cream Ridge Marl Company, Hornerstown	Distal end of right humerus

¹ **Shufeldt 1915** suggested the synonym *Limosavis* for *Graculavus*, but *G. velox* is still considered a limicoline shorebird. **Hope and Parris 2006** noted that *Graculavus* shows complex attachments and expanded humeral head, indicating strong wing muscles and powered flight.

² **Olson and Parris 1987** described this specimen, but concede that it is a "very poor specimen" and assigned it to *G. velox* because at the time it was the only known bird from the New Jersey fossil fauna. **Hope 2002** tentatively assigned this specimen to *G. velox*.

³ **Cracraft 1972** created the family **Telemtornithidae** for the genus *Telmatornis*

⁴ Synonyms include *T. affinis* **MARSH 1870** (YPM 840), *G. pumilus* **MARSH 1872** (YPM 850) and *P. vetus* **MARSH 1870** (ANSP 13361)

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
Charadriiformes (shorebirds)	"Form Family Graculavidae"		Hope 2004:360			
			YPM 850 Holotype of <i>G. pumilus</i> Marsh 1872:364, Shufeldt 1915:19, reclassified <i>T. priscus</i> by Olson & Parris 1987:6	Hornerstown	Hornerstown	Proximal end of right humerus with distal end of right carpometacarpus and several fragments of shafts of long bones.
			ANSP 15360 Olson & Parris 1987:6	Basal Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Left humerus lacking proximal end
			NJSM 11853 Olson & Parris 1987:6	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal end of left tarsometatarsus
			ANSP 15541 Olson & Parris 1987:10	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Right pedal phalanx I of digit II
			NJSM 11900 ⁵ Olson & Parris 1987:10 Hope 2004:360	Presumably from Hornerstown ⁶	Near Hornerstown, Upper Freehold Township	Proximal end of right ulna
			ANSP 13361 Holotype of <i>P. vetus</i> Marsh 1870:209 Shufeldt 1915:24 Olson & Parris 1987:6		Arneytown	Distal end of left tibiotarsus
			YPM 2808 ⁷ Miller 1955		Arneytown	Part of tibia
			<i>Laornis edwardsianus</i> March 1870	YPM 820 (Holotype) Marsh 1870:206 Shufeldt 1915:21	Basal Hornerstown	Pembertown Marl Company near Birmingham, Pemberton

⁵ Hope 2002 tentatively referred NJSM 11900 to *T. priscus*.

⁶ Olson and Parris 1987 indicate this specimen is from the Hornerstown formation, but it is unclear if it is from Cretaceous or Tertiary sediments.

⁷ YPM 2808 is listed in Miller 1955 as being collected near Arneytown, NJ and being "Eocene" and is also listed in Shufeldt 1915. The specimen cannot be located in the Yale collection. This specimen was originally described as *Graculavus pumilus* Marsh 1872

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
			Cracraft 1973:46 Olson & Parris:12		Township	
		<i>Palaeotringa littoralis</i> Marsh 1870	YPM 830 March 1870:208 Shufeldt 1915:23 Olson & Parris:12	Basal Hornerstown or Navesink	"Middle marl beds" near Hornerstown	Distal portion of left tibiotarsus lacking most of the inner condyle
		<i>Palaeotringa littoralis?</i> Marsh 1870	NJSM 11303 Olson & Parris 1987:14	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal portion of left humerus
		<i>Palaeotringa vagans</i> Marsh 1872	YPM 835 Marsh 1872:365 Shufeldt 1915:24 Olson & Parris:14	Basal Hornerstown or Navesink	Inversand Company, Sewell	Fragmented two- thirds of left tibiotarsus lacking external condyle and the anterior portion of the internal condyle.
		<i>Indeterminate</i>	NJSM 11302 Olson & Parris:14	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Abraded distal end of left humerus ,associated proximal portion of humeral shaft, end of radius, fragment shaft of ulna
<i>cf.</i> Procellariiformes (tube- nosed sea birds)	Tytthostonychidae	<i>Tytthostonyx glauconiticus</i> <i>Olson and Parris 1987</i>	NJSM 11341 (Holotype) Olson & Parris:16	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Right humerus lacking ventral tubercle. Portions of the pectoral crest and other parts of the proximal end.
	<i>Family and Genus Indeterminate</i>		ANSP 15713 Olson & Parris:16	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal portion of left ulna
<i>cf.</i> Palaeognathae	<i>cf. Lithornis sp.</i> Parris and Hope 2002		NJSM 15065 Parris & Hope 2002:115	Hornerstown	Crosswicks Creek, Upper Freehold Township	Right scapula, cranial end with part of the shaft.

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
Anseriformes (ducks, geese)	<i>Anseranatidae</i>	<i>Anatalavis rex</i> ⁸ Olson 1999	YPM 902 (Holotype) Shufeldt 1915:27 Cracraft 1972:41 Olson & Parris 1987:11 Olson 1999:233	Basal Hornerstown	Monmouth County	Humerus
			YPM 948 (Cotype) Shufeldt 1915:27 Cracraft 1972:41 Olson & Parris 1987:11	Hornerstown	Hornerstown	Paratypical left humerus lacking proximal end
<i>Neornithes, incertae sedis</i> (extant birds)		<i>Novacaesareala hungerfordi</i> ⁹ Parris and Hope 2002	NJSM 11302 Parris & Hope 2002:116	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Left forelimb fragments including the distal end and another midshaft section of the humerus, a midshaft section of the ulna, the proximal end and midshaft segments of the radius and other unidentified bone splinters, all associated in situ.
			ANSP 13361 ¹⁰ Parris & Hope 2002:121	Basal Hornerstown	Near Arneytown ¹¹	Distal end of left tibiotarsus
			NJSM 12119 Olson & Parris 1987:19 ¹²	Spoil Piles	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal end of left femur

⁸*Telmatornis rex* in Shufeldt, 1915, reassigned to Charadriiformes, and *Anatalavis rex* by Olson and Parris, 1987, Reassigned to Anseriformes by Olson 1999

⁹ Originally Assigned to *Graculavidae, incertae sedis* in Olson and Parris 198, reassigned to *Novacaesareala hungerfordi* Parris and Hope, 2002.

¹⁰ Baird (1967:261) determined that this specimen came from the “friable green marl near Arneytown” and was from the Basal Hornerstown.

¹¹ Holotype of *Palaeotringa vetus*, Marsh 1870, reclassified as *Telmatornis priscus*, Olson and Parris 1987, reclassified as *Neornithes*, Parris and Hope, 2002.

¹² Parris and Hope, 2002 listed this specimen as *Neornithes, incertae sedis*, whereas Olson and Parris, 1987 listed this specimen as *Aves, incertae sedis*.

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
<i>Neornithes, incertae sedis</i> (extant birds)		Genus and Species Indeterminate	NJSM 20692 This paper	Spoil Piles	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal right end of carpometacarpus
			NJSM 20693 This paper	Spoil Piles	Inversand Company, Sewell	Pedal phalange
			NJSM 21857 This paper	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	<i>cf.</i> carpometacarpus
			NJSM 21871 This paper	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	<i>cf.</i> tibiotarsus - shaft fragment
<i>cf. Aves</i> These specimens are listed in the NJSM catalog as being <i>Aves</i> , but they have not yet been formally described and require more in-depth study. They are included here for completeness.			NJSM 12248	MFL, Hornerstown	Inversand Company, Sewell	Long bone shaft fragment
			NJSM 15459 Listed as belonging to the Podicipediformes (Grebes)	Spoil Piles	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal tarsometarsus
			NJSM 15473	Spoil Piles	Inversand Company, Sewell	Distal end of tibatarsus
			NJSM 14152	Monmouth Group (Late Cretaceous)	Big Brook, Marlboro and Colts Neck Townships	Shaft fragment
			NJSM 16581	Marshalltown (Campanian)	Ellisdale Site, Crosswicks Creek, Upper Freehold Township	Identified as a bird coracoid, but could also be a lizard clavicle
			NJSM 16645			Possibly a proximal femur
			NJSM 16646			Proximal humerus. This bone has a set of three pneumatic pores just below the proximal end.
			NJSM 16741			Proximal femur
<i>cf. Aves</i> These specimens are listed in Shufeldt 1915:20 as possibly being <i>Graculavus sp.</i> , but even Shufeldt admits " <i>whether they be birds, mammals or reptiles, are worthless for the</i>			YPM 916, YPM 917	Navesink	Cream Ridge Marl Company, Hornerstown	Shafts of long bones

Order	Family	Genus/Species	Specimens	Formation	Locality (NJ)	Description
<p><i>purposes of identification". They are listed here for completeness since they could potentially represent some other Aves specimens from New Jersey.</i></p>						

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REFERENCES

- Baird, D., 1967. Age of Fossil Birds from the Greensands of New Jersey, *Auk*, 84:260-262
- Brodkorb, P., 1963. Birds from the Upper Cretaceous of Wyoming. *Proceedings of the XIIth International Ornithological Congress*, 55-70.
- Cracraft, J., 1972. A New Cretaceous Charadriiform Family, *Auk* 89:36-46.
- Cracraft, J., 1973. Systematics and evolution of the Gruiformes (Class Aves. 3. Phylogeny of the suborder Grues. *Bulletin American Museum Natural History*, 151:1-127.
- Gallagher, W.B., 1996. Marine ecosystem collapse and recovery across the K/T Boundary in New Jersey. In Gallagher, W.B. and D.C. Parris, editors, *Cenozoic and Mesozoic Vertebrate Paleontology of the New Jersey Coastal Plain, Investigation*, 5:46-50, New Jersey State Museum, Trenton.
- Gallagher, W.B. and D.C. Parris, 1996. Stratigraphy and paleontology at New Jersey's last marl mine, the Inversand Pit. In Gallagher, W.B. and D.C. Parris, editors, *Cenozoic and Mesozoic Vertebrate Paleontology of the New Jersey Coastal Plain, Investigation*, 5:42-46, New Jersey State Museum, Trenton.
- Hope, S. 2004. The Mesozoic radiation of Neornithes. In. Chiappe, L.M., Witmer, L.M., eds. *Mesozoic birds: above the heads of dinosaurs*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press, 339-388.
- Hope, S. and Parris, D.C., 2006. Biogeographic and Biostratigraphic significance of the Navesink/Hornerstown and Lance/Hell creek avifauna. GSA Meeting, Philadelphia, PA. 2006.
- Lambrecht, K., 1933. *Handbuch der Palaeornithologie*. 1024 pages. Berlin: Gebruder Borntraeger.
- Marsh, O.C., 1870. Notice of some fossil birds from the Cretaceous and Tertiary Formations of the United States. *American Journal of Science, Series 2*, 49:205-217.
- Marsh, O.C., 1872. Preliminary Description of *Hesperonis regalis*, with notices of four other new species of Cretaceous Birds. *American Journal of Science, Series 3*, 3:360-365.
- Marsh, O.C., 1873. Fossil birds from the Cretaceous of North America. *American Journal of Science, Series 3*, 5:229-231.

- Marsh, O.C., 1877. Notice of some new vertebrate fossils. *American Journal of Science*, series 3, 14: 251-253.
- Miller, H.W., Jr. A Check-list of the Cretaceous and Tertiary Vertebrates of New Jersey. *Journal of Paleontology*, 29(5):903-914.
- Olson, S. L., 1985. The fossil records of birds; in D.S. Farner, J.R. King, and K.C. Parkes (eds.), *Avian Biology*, Vol. 8. Academic Press, New York.
- Olson, S.L., 1996. The Anseriform Relationships of *Anatalavis* Olson and Parris (Anseranatidae), with a New Species from the Lower Eocene London Clay. In Olson, S.L., editor, *Avian Paleontology at the Close of the 20th Century: Proceedings of the 4th International Meeting of the Society for Avian Paleontology and Evolution, Washington, D.C., 4-7 June 1996*. *Smithsonian Contributions to Paleobiology*, 89:231-243.
- Olson, S.L., and D.C Parris, 1987. The Cretaceous Birds of New Jersey. *Smithsonian Contributions to Paleobiology*, Number 63:1-22.
- Parris, D.C., 1986. Biostratigraphy of the Fossil Crocodile *Hyposaurus* Owen from New Jersey. *Investigation No. 4, New Jersey State Museum, March 1986, Trenton*.
- Parris, D.C., and S. Hope, 2002. New interpretations of birds from the Hornerstown and Navesink formations, New Jersey; in Zhou Z. (ed.), *Proceedings of the 5th International Meeting of the Society of Avian Paleontology and Evolution, Beijing, June, 2000*. China Science Press.
- Rapp, W.F., 1943. List of the Fossil Birds of New Jersey, *Journal of Paleontology* 17(1):124.
- Richards, H.G., and W.B. Gallagher, 1974. The problem of the Cretaceous-Tertiary boundary in New Jersey. *Notulae Naturae*, Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia. 449:1-6.
- Shufeldt, R.W., 1915. Fossil Birds in the Marsh Collection of Yale University. *Transactions of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences*, 19:1-110.
- Wetmore, A, 1930. The Age of Supposed Cretaceous Birds from New Jersey, *Auk*, 47(2):186-187.
- Wetmore, A., 1940. A Check-list of Fossil Birds of North America, *Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections*, 99(4):1-81.
- Wetmore, A., 1956. A checklist of the fossil and prehistoric birds of North America and the West Indies. *Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections*, 131:1-105.